

LINGUOCULTUROLOGY IN RUSSIAN LANGUAGE STUDY

Urinova Shoira Pulatovna

Lecturer, Fergana State University

Azizova Mukhnora Madaminjon kizi

Lecturer, Fergana State University

Pulatova Dilshoda Bakhtiyor kizi

Lecturer, Fergana State University

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Abstract: This article examines the role of the precedent name in the formation of linguistic and cultural competence of students in the classroom of Russian as a foreign language. The authors analyze the methods and techniques of using precedent names for a deeper understanding of Russian culture and its features.

Keywords: precedent name, linguistic and cultural competence, Russian as a foreign language, cultural context, teaching methods, adaptation, communication.

Linguistic and cultural competence involves the analysis and systematization of manifestations of the material and spiritual components of culture into a living spoken language, interpretation and correlation of the meanings of words and expressions.

The cultural connotation of complex units of discourse involves a comprehensive analysis of lexical units, taking into account their additional meaning accepted in a certain cultural environment, as well as related semantic functions arising under the influence of ethnic, geographical, professional and other features.

Lexical units provoke the emergence of an associative series in a linguistic personality, that is, the essence of a lexical unit becomes publicly available and reproducible.

Any language has both neutral and emotionally colored lexemes. The latter, most often, have a secondary nomination, which directly depends on the cultural characteristics of native speakers. This creates certain difficulties when learning foreign languages, because without immersion in the culture of native speakers, students have completely different associations.

As a rule, the greatest difficulties are observed in understanding precedent phenomena, the interpretation of which is impossible without an appropriate linguistic and cultural commentary given by the educational material or prepared by a teacher.

Among the studied precedent phenomena, precedent names are singled out separately, that is, "individual names associated: a) with a widely known text, which, as a rule, belongs to the number of precedent; b) with a situation widely known to native speakers and acting as precedent" [Gudkov 2003: 106]. Knowledge and understanding of case names indicates the level of knowledge of a foreign language of the student. The use of precedent names in speech reflects the characteristic features of the speaker, makes his speech clearer, richer and more emotional. To achieve this level of linguistic personality, it is necessary to use material closely related to Russian culture, ethnic and historical features of the country of the language being studied in the RCT classes.

In colloquial speech, precedent names are most often used to give the dialogue the greatest expression. Their correct selection reflects not only the general emotional mood, but also demonstrates a wide range of relationships between the interlocutors. In this case, another aspect of the precedent name is manifested — the pragmatic one.

The precedent name allows you to convey the meaning of the message with reference to the cultural heritage as vividly and figuratively as possible. It appeals to the image that carries the primary nominative. For example, in most cases, Cinderella is associated with an unhappy girl who works hard, the Snow Queen can be called a person who is emotionless, Malvina causes the association of a girl with bright hair, the Ugly Duckling is interpreted with a not very handsome person, etc.

Learning and being able to correctly interpret a case name is important for:

1. Preventing mistakes, misunderstandings and unpleasant situations when communicating with native speakers.
2. Understanding authentic texts when reading.
3. Making your own speech more expressive.

The semantic load of the precedent name when reading becomes a symbol reflecting the plot. It translates a precedent situation, which is directly related to and, as a result, a precedent text, that is, the development of one precedent name involves the development of significant cultural material.

Thus, the use of a precedent name is important for the formation of linguistic and cultural competence of a foreign student in the structure of communicative competence. The demonstration of precedent phenomena in RCT classes contributes to the formation of a second language personality,

allows you to adequately perceive the meaning of statements, to verbalize your own epistles in an accessible and competent way.

Significant difficulties in RCT classes arise when structuring the presentation of case material, which is due to the characteristic features of individual lexical

units and ways to explain them. Precedent names in the study of the Russian language by foreign students are very voluminous and difficult. They require close attention and separate study. E.B.Ushakova in her article suggests the following algorithm of actions when working with a precedent name:

1. Presentation of additional reference material containing an explanation of the new case name, to non-diagnostic texts.

2. Analysis of the invariant of perception, concluded in the context of the studied material, to focus on the distinctive features of a precedent name new to students.

3. The use of the studied case names in further work in order to eliminate errors in interpretation when using.

4. Consolidation of new material by separate exercises.

5. The use of precedent expressions directly in speech [Ushakova 2014: 16].

The gradual formation of a linguistic personality, which is based on certain character traits, ways of thinking, is directly related to the co-study of the language and culture

of its native speakers, culture in a broad sense. The task of the teacher is to introduce foreign students

students' interest in Russian culture, history, and traditions. Here, a significant role is assigned to precedent names as carriers of cultural information, giving imagery and expressiveness to speech. Such knowledge contributes to a deep immersion in Russian culture, an understanding of the national mentality and the improvement of the language being studied.

Reference:

1. Gudkov D.B. Theory and practice of intercultural communication. M.: Gnosis, 2003. 286 p.

2. Krasnykh V.V. "One's own" among "strangers": myth or reality. Moscow: ITDGC "Gnosis", 2003. 375 p.

3. Krasnykh V.V. Ethnopsycholinguistics and linguoculturology. Moscow: ITDGC "Gnosis", 2002. 254 p.

4. Ushakova E.B. The phenomenon of a precedent name in linguoculturology and the aspect of teaching Russian language as a foreign language // Bulletin of the Moscow State University. 2014. No. 2. 16 with

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